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Can Service Learning foster a Civic Responsibility by VET-students? – Empirical results of a explorative, process-oriented pilot study

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Abstract

One aim in Vocational Education and Training (VET) is to foster students' competencies for future working fields as well as a personal development regarding their future role in the society. With this in mind, service learning represents a suitable way to reach these aims in VET. In service learning, students participate in a service activity that meets a community need, while reflection on this activity in turn fosters a deeper understanding of the academic content and develops students' values and attitudes towards civic responsibility. Nevertheless, the effects of service learning in VET-schools have not been examined in research so far. Therefore, the following study presents empirical results of an explorative, process-oriented pilot study on what situations in service learning stimulate VET students to think about civic responsibility. In result, three situation types are revealed: 'getting insights into volunteering activities', 'working on the service project' and 'awareness about civic engagement'.

Keywords

service learning; VET-system; civic responsibility; process-oriented data

1 Introduction: service learning and VET

One aim in Vocational Education and Training (VET) is to foster students' competencies for future working fields as well as a personal development regarding their future role in society (e.g. Gerholz & Brahm 2014). From an instructional perspective, the approach of service learning represents a suitable way to reach these aims in VET. In service learning, students participate in a service activity that meets a community need, while reflection on this activity in turn fosters a deeper understanding of the academic content and develops students' values and attitudes towards civic responsibility (Bringle & Clayton 2012). Thus, service learning combines academic knowledge acquisition with civic engagement and is based on the assumption of problem-based learning (Gerholz et al. 2017, Dewey 1966). In the last decades, a growing number of higher education institutions have implemented service learning as an educational approach (Kenworthy-U'ren 2008), however, in the VET-system and vocational schools respectively service learning is not common. Therefore, the effects of service learning in VET have not been examined in research so far. This is surprising since the service learning approach aligns with the aims of VET. The following paper aims to present results of an explorative, process-oriented pilot study on how civic responsibility can be fostered during service learning by VET students.

2 Theoretical grounding

Fostering of a civic responsibility is one main intention of service learning (Deeley 2015). However, from a theoretical point of view, there is no uniform understanding of this construct

in the service learning discourse. Deeley points out that during service learning, the sense of citizenship should be increased. Sense of citizenship comprises “civic virtues of civility, trust, public spiritedness, active participation and engagement” (Deeley 2015, 24). It is obvious that the understanding of Deeley includes an improved civic engagement and a more socio-political activity. This is similar to Toncar et al. (2006), who describe it as social responsibility. In contrast, Prentice & Robinson (2010) distinguish between citizenship and civic responsibility. Citizenship includes tolerance for and interaction with different cultures. Civic responsibility means an active contribution to the community or civil society respectively, as well as believing in a positive impact on social challenges (Prentice & Robinson 2010, 5).

A varying understanding can also be found in the existing empirical studies. Meta-Analyses revealed positive effects of service learning to foster civic responsibility. For instance, Yorio & Ye showed in a meta-analysis a positive effect of understanding social issues ($\eta = .34$), Conway et al. (2009) revealed a positive effect ($d = .27$) for citizenship understanding and Celio et al. (2011) found a positive effect ($d = .17$) for civic engagement. Celio et al. (2011, 170) used the term ‘civic engagement’, which includes altruism, responsibility and voting behavior. Conway et al. (2009, 235) speaks of ‘citizenship understanding’ that comprises personal-responsible, participatory and justice-oriented citizenship. In contrast, Yorio & Ye (2012, 11) used the term ‘understanding social issues’ that comprises things like cultural awareness, perception of the homeless, ethical and moral values and decision making. The existing meta-analyses show positive effects of service learning to foster civic responsibility, although the studies follow different understandings and models of this construct. However, single studies revealed no such effects (Reinders 2010, Prentice & Robinson 2010).

All in all, two limitations can be described. One the one hand, a uniform understanding of civic responsibility cannot be found. But the understanding in the studies of civic responsibility is quite similar, referring to attitudes towards the civil society, the social and personal responsibility of an individual as well as the willingness to be engaged (Gerholz et al. 2018, 66). Therefore, it seems relevant to take a look into the situations experienced by students during a service learning arrangement. A second limitation in these studies is the retrospective measurement of changes regarding civic responsibility. A process-oriented approach can reduce distortions and help to gain indications on design parameters that are relevant for the sensitization for civic matters (Rausch 2014, Gerholz et al. 2018). Therefore, the following study in VET-system examines the research question:

- What effects does a service learning arrangement have on VET students’ development regarding civic attitudes?
- What are the key situations in a service learning arrangement which stimulate VET students to think about civic responsibility?

3 Method

The study is based on a case study of a full-time vocational school (school of commerce) in the VET-System in Germany. In this school, a service learning arrangement according to a problem-based learning approach was implemented. The service project for the students ($n = 55$) was the implementation of a marketing event for a charitable organization. The students worked in groups and this was linked to in-class education.

To examine the effect of the Service Learning course on students’ development regarding civic attitudes a pretest-posttest group design with a questionnaire was used. The questionnaire included among others the ‘Civic Attitude Scale (CAS)’ (Mabry, 1998; five items; example: “Individuals have a responsibility to help solve our social problems.”). Each of these

variables was assessed on a six-point Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree) ($\alpha_1 = .62$, $\alpha_2 = 0.86$).

To describe the key situations which stimulate VET students to think about civic responsibility, a weekly journal was developed. This journal was based on the diary method (Rausch 2014, Gerholz et al. 2018). In the weekly journal, students were requested to record their experiences that led them to think about civic responsibility. Each journal entry comprised six items containing qualitative data (description of the experience and reasons for the thinking) and quantitative data (intensity of the experience, number of persons involved, time and characterization of the experience). The data were analyzed according to a qualitative content analysis (Schreier 2012) in an inductive way to categorize the key situations regarding civic responsibility during the service learning arrangement.

4 First results

Table 1 displays the descriptive statistics of the civic attitudes scale. There is a decline in the means from t1 to t2, however, a t-Test showed no significant results ($t(28) = 1.10$, $p = .281$). The standard deviations show a higher spectrum in t2 to t1. Thus, a positive or negative effect could not be found. From a descriptive point of view, there is a decline in the civic attitudes, but there is a higher spectrum in the answers in t2. This could indicate that the students reflect more deeply about their civic attitudes through the service learning arrangement.

Table 1 Quantitative data of Civic attitudes in t1 and t2

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Civic attitudes t1	29	2.80	5.60	4.56	0.81
Civic attitudes t2	29	1.80	6.00	4.23	1.25

Regarding the weekly journals, in total, 385 journal entries (55 students x 7 weeks) were possible and 289 were completed. 143 journals contained a description of an experience for data analysis. The qualitative content analysis indicates that these situations can be classified into five different types. Situation type 1 means ‘insights into volunteering activities’ (e.g. *“we’ve got to know different volunteering activities and were informed about the reasons for volunteering”* 03042002; w1). Type 2 refers to situations where the students develop an awareness for civic responsibility (e.g. *“by helping and supporting others there is a feeling that I also help to make a better world”* 18032004; w1). Situation type 3 comprises situations where ‘interaction with peers’ was the trigger to think about civic engagement (e.g. *“I thought and read about the activities with my friends”* 02082004; w7). Situation type 4 were situations in which the students work on the service project (e.g. *“We thought about the design of the stage during the marketing event”* 03042002; w3). Situation type 5 means situations where the students interact or talk with the community partner (e.g. *“We have talked with Mr. (.) about volunteering in the charity organization”* 29052004, w4).

Table 2 Types of key situations and distribution

	Amount of situations
Insights into volunteering activities	40
Development of awareness for civic responsibility	27
Interaction with peers	12
Working on the service project	76
Interaction with the community partner	4

In Table 2 the distribution of the identified types of situations is presented. To sum up, the results show that situations ‘working on the service project’ and ‘insights into volunteering activities’ influences thinking about civic engagement. The third most frequent situations are situations where the students develop an awareness for civic responsibility. Above all, this situation type seems more relevant to foster a civic responsibility during service learning.

5 Conclusion

The intention of the papers was to present initial results of a process-oriented pilot study on how civic responsibility can be fostered during service learning by VET students. The quantitative data shows no significant effects; however, a descriptive decline between the beginning and the end of the service learning arrangement can be shown. Regarding the key situations, it seems that ‘working on the service project’ and getting ‘insights into volunteering activities’ are the most important triggers, in which the students thought about civic matters. In light of the key situations, it is surprising that there is a decline of civic attitudes in the quantitative data. An explanation could be that during the service learning arrangements the students think deeper about civic matters and their positions to civic engagement. An indication for this explanation is also the higher standard deviation in t2. Furthermore, it has to be taken into account that only one third of all possible descriptions of an experience with civic engagement are documented in the weekly journals.

The analysis of the data is still ongoing. In addition, interviews were conducted at the end of the service learning arrangement in regards to the perceptions and appraisals of the students. Here, more information about the reasons for the situation types can be surveyed. All in all, the weekly journals are an appropriate instruments to make the experienced situations during a service learning arrangement more visible. For future research a broader database for the key situations seems relevant.

References

- Bringle, R. G. & Clayton, P. H. (2012). Civic Education through Service Learning: What, How, and Why?. In L. McIlrath, A. Lyons & R. Munck (Eds.), *Higher Education and Civic Engagement. Comparative Perspectives* (pp. 101-123), New York: Palgrave Macmillan
- Celio, C., Durlak, J., & Dymnicki, A. (2011). A meta-analysis of the impact of service-learning on students. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 34(2), 164-181. doi: 10.1177/105382591103400205
- Conway J., Amel, E., & Gerwien, D. (2009). Teaching and learning in the social context. A meta-analysis of service learning’s effects on academic, personal, social, and citizenship outcomes. *Teaching of Psychology*, 36(4), 233-245. doi: 10.1080/00986280903172969
- Deeley, S. J. (2010). Service-learning: thinking outside the box. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 11(1), 43-53. doi: 10.1177/1469787409355870
- Deeley, S. J. (2015). *Critical perspectives on service-learning in higher education*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Dewey, J. (1966 [1916]). *Democracy and education*. New York, NY: Free Press.
- Gerholz, K.-H., Holzner, J., & Rausch, A. (2018). Where is the Civic Responsibility in Service Learning? A Process-oriented Empirical Study. *Journal for Higher Education Development*, Vol. 13/I. (2), 61-80. DOI: 10.3217/zfhe-13-02/04
- Gerholz, K.-H., Liszt, V., & Klingsieck, K. (2017). Effects of learning design patterns in Service Learning courses. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 19(1), 47-59.. doi: 10.1177/1469787417721420.
- Gerholz, K.-H. & Brahm, T. (2014): *Apprenticeship and Vocational Education*. In: C. Harteis, **CROSSING BOUNDARIES IN VET 2019**

- , A. Rausch, & J. Seifried (Eds.): Discourses on professional learning: On the boundary between learning and working. Dordrecht: Springer.
- Mabry, J. B. (1998). Pedagogical variations in service-learning and student outcomes: How time, contact, and reflection matter. *Michigan Journal of Community Service Learning*, 5, 32-47.
- Prentice, M. & Robinson, G. (2010). Improving student learning outcomes with service learning. American Association of Community Colleges. Retrieved from http://www.aacc.nche.edu/Resources/aaccprograms/horizons/Documents/slorb_jan2010.pdf.
- Rausch, A. (2014). Using diaries in research on work and learning. In C. Harteis, A. Rausch, & J. Seifried (Eds.), Discourses on professional learning: On the boundary between learning and working (pp. 341-366). Dordrecht: Springer. DOI 10.1007/978-94-007-7012-6_17
- Reinders H. (2010). Lernprozesse durch Service Learning an Universitäten. *Zeitschrift für Pädagogik*, 56 (4), 531-547.
- Toncar, M. F., Reid, J. S., Burns, D. J., Anderson, C. E., & Nguyen, H. P. (2006). Uniform assessment of the benefits of service learning: the development, evaluation and implementation of the SELEB scale. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 14(3), 233-248. doi: [10.2753/MTP1069-6679140304](https://doi.org/10.2753/MTP1069-6679140304)
- Yorio, P. L. & Ye, F. (2012). A Meta-Analysis on the Effects of Service-Learning on the Social, Personal, and Cognitive Outcomes of Learning. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 11(1), 9–27. doi: [10.5465/amle.2010.0072](https://doi.org/10.5465/amle.2010.0072)

Biographical notes

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